

Research article

New data on the occurrence and status of some sparid species (Actinopterygii: Sparidae) in the coastal Bulgarian Black Sea waters

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Abstract: Fish species diversity in the Black Sea is affected by a phenomenon called mediterraneanisation. This is related to the advance of thermophilic fish from the Mediterranean Sea into the Black Sea. Although sparid species have been noted in the Black Sea, detailed information regarding their occurrence and recent status remains limited. In 2022–2023, we collected data on three sparid species in Bulgarian coastal waters. These species included *Spicara smaris* (Linnaeus 1758), *Lithognathus mormyrus* (Linnaeus 1758), and *Diplodus puntazzo* (Walbaum 1792). This study provides new localities and quantitative data for these sparid species in the coastal zone of Bulgarian Black Sea.

Keywords: Black Sea, mediterraneanisation, range expansion, Sparidae

Introduction

The advance of thermophilic fish from the Mediterranean Sea to the Black Sea is often called mediterraneanisation (Micu & Todorova, 2009). This process has recently attracted increasing attention, because thermophilic species are considered effective indicators of climate change. The expansion of thermophilic fish into the Black Sea offers direct evidence of the relationship between climate change and the distribution patterns of Mediterranean Sea fish (Shiganova & Ozturk, 2009; Hidalgo et al., 2018). The Black Sea is characterised by low-salinity waters, anoxic conditions below 200 m, and higher productivity than the Mediterranean Sea, however, it supports a lower level of biodiversity (Miladinova et al., 2017; Shlyakhov & Daskalov, 2008; Hidalgo et al., 2018). The fish fauna of the Black Sea is comprised of a complex and dynamic assemblage of indigenous relic species and Mediterranean immigrants. The current ichthyofauna in the Black

Sea comprises approximately 190 species (Yankova et al., 2014). Analysis of the geographic origin of marine fish species indicated that the majority (59.3%) had an Atlantic-Mediterranean origin, 7.4% were cosmopolitan, 31.2% were Ponto-Caspian relics (endemic to the region), and 2.1% were introduced species (Yankova et al., 2014). All sparids in the Black Sea belong to the group of the Atlantic-Mediterranean species. Documentation of their range expansion and quantity variation provides insights into species adaptability and dynamics, which are essential for evaluating their impact on the Black Sea ecosystem. Despite this expansion, information on the distribution and biomass of these fish species is scarce, particularly in the Bulgarian sector of the Black Sea.

This study used the data obtained from small-scale fisheries and pelagic trawlers. The information collected revealed the occurrence and fluctuations of the three Sparidae fish species in coastal waters. These are *Spicara smaris* (Linnaeus 1758), *Litho-*

Table 1. Collected data of Sparidae fish in 2022–2023 and collection methods applied along the Bulgarian Black Sea waters – OTM (midwater otter trawl), mesh size 16, and 18 mm, trawl length 27 m, trawl width 6, and 12 m; GNS (anchored gillnets), mesh size 32 mm, length 200 m, height 2,5 m.

Species	Finding date	Fishing gear type	Coordinates		Depth (m)
			Latitude	Longitude	
<i>S. smaris</i>	13.09.2022	OTM/18 mm	43.193	28.061	18–21
	1.11.2022	OTM/18 mm	42.982	27.926	26–27
	1.11.2022	OTM/16 mm	42.970	27.947	23–27
	2.11.2022	OTM/18 mm	43.067	27.949	24–27
	2.11.2022	OTM/16 mm	43.063	27.942	24–29
	10.11.2022	OTM/18 mm	43.182	28.022	23
	11.11.2022	OTM/18 mm	42.951	27.947	24–27
	15.11.2022	OTM/18 mm	43.381	28.527	32
	18.11.2022	OTM/16 mm	42.890	27.946	30–33
	31.8.2023	OTM/18 mm	42.979	27.925	25–26
	31.8.2023	OTM/18 mm	42.978	27.924	25–26
	31.8.2023	OTM/18 mm	43.048	27.929	25–26
	31.8.2023	OTM/18 mm	42.980	27.923	25–26
	31.8.2023	GNS	42.895	27.902	1–5
	6.10.2023	OTM/18 mm	42.261	27.980	42–43
13.10.2023	OTM/16 mm	42.808	28.036	32–35	
<i>L. mormyrus</i>	28.8.2023	GNS	42.902	27.901	1–5
<i>D. puntazzo</i>	30.8.2023	GNS	42.912	27.899	1–5

gnathus mormyrus (Linnaeus 1758), and *Diplodus puntazzo* (Walbaum 1792). The primary objective of this study was to provide updated records and some quantitative population parameters, as well as to highlight the range expansion of these species along the Bulgarian Black Sea coast.

Material and methods

This study implemented a research strategy that incorporated data obtained from small-scale fisheries and pelagic trawlers between 2022 (21 fishing days from September to November) and 2023 (20 fishing days from August to October). This approach allowed us to record different Sparidae species caught as bycatch in the Bulgarian Black Sea waters (Table 1).

The pelagic trawlers operated along the Bulgarian coast between Cape Kaliakra and Tsarevo. In

addition, data from small fishing boats with passive fishing gear (bottom gillnets) were tracked near Byala and Kara Dere (Fig. 1).

The total length and weight of the collected sparid specimens were measured onboard the fishing vessel and recorded to the nearest 1 mm and 1 g, respectively. Species names followed the classification of Fricke et al. (2024).

The calculation of catch per unit area (CPUA) for the OTM pelagic trawlers followed the methodology described by Mihneva et al. (2023). For GNS gillnets, CPUA was determined based on the net dimensions of 200 m length and 2.5 m height, resulting in an effective swept area of 500 m². To account for variations in deployment duration, a time factor was incorporated into the calculation, as the trawling duration varied between 0.42–4.07 hours for OTM and 168–312 hours for GNS. The final CPUA (kg/km²) was calculated using the following equation:

Fig. 1. Map of fishing localities (41 fishing days in total) in 2022 (red dots) and 2023 (white dots).

$$CPUA = \text{total catch} / a(\text{km}^2) \times \text{time}(h),$$

where:

- total catch is the amount (kg) of Sparidae species caught,
- “a” is the swept area (converted to km²),
- time is the duration of the operation (in hours).

To standardise the catches of *S. smarís* across different sampling conditions and gear types, a Generalized Linear Model (GLM) was employed. The initial model included gear type, month, depth, and geographic coordinates (latitude and longitude) as explanatory variables. Prior to running the GLM, the CPUA values of *S. smarís* were square root

transformed to stabilise the variance and improve normality assumptions. The optimal lambda value, which balances model complexity and predictive accuracy, was determined through cross-validation using the glmnet package in the XLSTAT software (Version 2023.3.0, Addinsoft). The final GLM included the following significant predictors:

$$\text{SQRT(CPUA)} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Year} + \beta_2 \text{Depth} + \beta_3 (\text{Longitude} \times \text{Latitude}) + \epsilon$$

where:

- β_0 is the intercept (estimated at 485.303),
- β_1 is the coefficient for Year (9.491),
- β_2 is the coefficient for Depth (-0.334),
- β_3 is the interaction coefficient for Longitude \times Latitude (-20.142),
- ϵ represents the error term (residual standard error: 13.64).

The inclusion of these terms was justified by their statistically significant effects on the *S. smarís* catch quantity, as determined by model validation.

For the other two species, the GLM was not applied because they were collected as single catches using only the GNS gear.

Results and discussion

We documented the presence and some quantitative parameters of three sparid species in the coastal waters of the Bulgarian Black Sea – *S. smarís*, *L. mormyrus*, and *D. puntazzo*. Among them *S. smarís* was the most frequently observed at a total of 16 different locations, mostly along the central and southern coasts, with catch quantities ranging from 0.01 to 405.9 kg/km², and medium sizes ranging from 7.9 to 12.4 cm in length and 5.6 to 19.9 g in weight (Table 2). This species was mostly caught at depths below 30 m. It should be noted that the catch of *S. smarís* was very low during the autumn observations of 2022, ranging from 0.01 to 0.9 kg/km², and increased in 2023 indicating significant fluctuations in the species' quantities. This species can reach a maximum length of 21 cm (Tsangridis & Filippoussis, 1988), although the most commonly observed size in the Black Sea is between 11–14 cm (Ismen, 1995). The spawning season of *S. smarís* in the Mediterranean region begins in February and ends in May (Karlou-Riga et al., 2000), whereas in the Eastern Black Sea, it occurs between May and June (Şahin & Genç, 1999). This difference in spawning

seasons is attributed to a variety of factors, including climate, habitat conditions, and food availability. The individuals we found along the Bulgarian Black Sea coast were smaller with length of 7.9–9.2 cm. This species was initially reported in the Black Sea near the coast of Crimea in the second half of 19th century (Kessler, 1860). The first record of *S. smarís* along the Bulgarian Black Sea coast was in 1952 (Stojanov, 1954), based on a single specimen caught near Cape Galata, Varna District. Later, it was considered as very rare for the Bulgarian coast by Stoyanov et al. (1963). This species has also been reported in overview studies by Karapetkova & Zivkov (1995), Zivkov et al. (2006), Stefanov (2007) and Yankova et al. (2014). Our data show that the quantity of *S. smarís* fluctuate significantly but the species become recently more abundant along the Bulgarian coast. According to Lloret et al. (2014), thermophilic species have three phases of colonisation (occasional occurrence, common presence, and establishment). Based on our recent survey, we consider *S. smarís* an established species in the Bulgarian part of the Black Sea.

Lithognathus mormyrus was first discovered in 1958 in the Black Sea near Varna Bay, Bulgaria (Stoyanov et al., 1963). Subsequently, this species was recorded along the coast of Romania (Stanciu & Ilie, 1980) and recently near the Crimean and Georgian Coast of the Black Sea and Cape Aya (Bolatchev et al., 2013; Guchmanidze & Boltachev, 2017; Maltsev & Vasilets, 2020; Guskov et al., 2022). This species has also been reported along the Turkish coast of the Black Sea (Satilmis et al., 2014; Engin et al., 2015; Aydin, 2018; Aydin & Sözer, 2019; Kasapoğlu et al., 2020; Karadurmuş & Aydin, 2021). Although the species was reported in the Black Sea from the Bulgarian coast for the first time, it was not detected again along it afterwards. We found *L. mormyrus* in the shallow waters around Byala (depths 1–5 m) near the mouth of the Fandakliyska River on 28 August 2023 (Table 1). This is the second record of this species from the Bulgarian Black Sea waters. The total CPUA is 238.1 kg/km² with an average length and weight of 18.1 cm and 87 g, respectively (Table 2), which is a significant recent increase of the population of *L. mormyrus* in the Bulgarian coastal waters. The adaptation of this species to Black Sea conditions has been demonstrated by the presence of juveniles near the coast of Sevastopol and spawned individuals near the coast of Abkhazia (Dbar et al.,

Table 2. Standardised catch data, length, and weight of different species per locality during 2022–2023.

Species	Date of catch	CPUA [kg/km ²]	Mean length (min–max) [cm]	Mean weight (min–max) [g]
<i>S. smaris</i>	13.09.2022	0.01	7.9 (7.3–8.1)	5.61 (5.8–6.6)
	1.11.2022	0.21	9.5 (8.7–10.3)	8.33 (5.8–10.9)
	1.11.2022	0.23	9.6	8.5
	2.11.2022	0.21	9.7	8.8
	2.11.2022	0.31	8.6	6.2
	10.11.2022	0.17	8.8 (8.0–9.5)	6.7 (5.1–8.6)
	11.11.2022	0.19	8.9 (8.5–9.4)	7.2 (6.5–7.9)
	15.11.2022	0.86	8.9	7.1
	18.11.2022	0.10	9.2 (8.7–9.6)	7.7 (6.0–9.2)
	31.8.2023	238.80	12.3 (11.0–14.3)	19.1 (12.4–32.6)
	31.8.2023	72.52	12.3 (11.1–14.4)	19.9 (12.2–33.2)
	31.8.2023	196.54	12.4 (10.9–14.3)	18.8 (11.8–31.1)
	31.8.2023	58.30	12.2 (11.0–13.7)	19.7 (13.3–25.6)
	31.8.2023	385.98	12.4 (11.1–14.2)	19.0 (12.9–32.1)
	6.10.2023	405.87	11.0 (10.2–12.0)	14.3 (11.6–18.0)
13.10.2023	122.58	10.9 (9.9–13.2)	14.3 (10.5–24.9)	
<i>L. mormyrus</i>	28.8.2023	238.10	18.1 (12.1–20.1)	87.0 (23.8–107.1)
<i>D. puntazzo</i>	30.8.2023	454.55	19.3 (15.2–22.3)	114.8 (56.3–167.8)

2020; Karpova, 2020). Although this species has been reported to reproduce in the Black Sea, further research is required to determine its spawning locations and spawning periods in this area. In the present study, we considered *L. mormyrus* to be an occasional species in the Bulgarian part of the Black Sea until we found evidence of spawning in the region.

Diplodus puntazzo is a Mediterranean-Atlantic species which also occurs in the coastal waters of the Black Sea (Svetovidov, 1964; Bat et al., 2005; Fricke et al., 2007; Vasileva, 2007; Keskin, 2010; Yankova et al., 2014). It is considered a rare and temporary inhabitant of the Bulgarian Black Sea coastal waters, occurring in the late spring, summer, and autumn months from June to October (Drensky, 1948, 1951; Gueorguiev et al., 1960; Manolov, 1970). According to Gueorguiev et al. (1960), this species does not reproduce along the Bulgarian coast. There are no recently published data on the distribution and

quantitative parameters of *D. puntazzo* in the Bulgarian Black Sea waters. During the current survey, we caught the species near Byala and at the mouth of the Fandakliyska River at a depths of 1–5 m. The CPUA was 454.6 kg/km², and the fish had a mean length of 19.3 cm and a mean weight of 114.8 g (Table 2). Although the species has been noted to reproduce in the southern part of the Black Sea in Türkiye (Aydın & Özdemir, 2021), there is still no evidence for its spawning along the Bulgarian coast. Therefore, we consider *D. puntazzo* to be an occasional species in the Bulgarian Black Sea coastal waters.

The identified Sparidae fish are classified as omnivorous and hermaphroditic, which provides certain advantages for expanding their range. Furthermore, their ability to adapt to the Black Sea's climatic changes is facilitated by the region's projected warming (Schaltout & Omstedt, 2014). The northward expansion of Mediterranean thermophilic

species is probably the most detectable biotic response to climate change in this region. The effect of the recent increase in seawater temperature (Mohamed et al., 2022; Polonsky & Serebrennikov, 2023) may support the migration of other Mediterranean species into the Black Sea and increase their adaptation and establishment, which will have an impact on the Black Sea ecosystem.

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Authors' contributions

(using [CrediT](#))

Feriha M. Tserkova: conceptualisation, investigation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Vesselina V. Mihneva: conceptualisation, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Elitsa P. Petrova-Pavlova: conceptualisation, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Tihomir Stefanov: writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Krasimir Georgiev: investigation; Stanimir Valchev: investigation; Zahari Marinov: investigation; Mak Goranov: investigation; Radinela Stefanova: investigation; Lidia Nedkova: investigation.

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